

1 **Impacts of Plant Roots on Debris-Flow Bed Erosion in**
2 **Laboratory Experiments**

3 **Anna J. van den Broek¹, Dagmar T. Mennes¹, Maarten G. Kleinhans¹,**
4 **Lonneke Roelofs¹, Jana Eichel¹, Daniel Draebing¹, Tjalling de Haas¹**

5 ¹Department of Physical Geography, Utrecht University, Utrecht, 3584 CB, The Netherlands
6

Corresponding author: Anna J. van den Broek, a.j.vandenbroek@uu.nl

7

Abstract

8

9

10

11

12

13

14

15

16

17

18

19

20

21

22

23

24

Debris flows often increase in size due to bed erosion and entrainment, enhancing their hazardous potential. However, the effects of plant rooting on debris-flow erosion on ubiquitous vegetated slopes remain unknown, which hinders debris-flow hazard assessment. Here, we investigated the effects of roots on debris-flow bed erosion using scaled experiments in a 5 m long, 0.3 m wide laboratory flume with an erodible bed. Roots of fast-growing *Sorghum bicolor* (Sudan grass) seedlings were used as proxies for tree roots to quantify the effect of varying rooting characteristics on erosion. Our results indicate that erosion decreases non-linearly with increasing Root Length Density (*RLD*) and Root Area Ratio (*RAR*). Increases in either parameter enhance root–soil contact, thereby improving soil stability and reducing erosion. Among the two, *RLD*, and thus the combined effect of root length and root density, appears most influential, as *RAR* does not capture the three-dimensional structure of the root system. Our experimental results suggest that increasing root-soil contact at the debris-flow bed reduces erosion, decreasing or even preventing debris-flow volume growth. These findings imply that alterations in vegetation characteristics, such as those resulting from forest fires or reforestation, affect debris-flow erosion and open up possibilities for biogeomorphic scale experiments for slope processes.

25

26

Keywords: *debris flow, erosion, vegetation roots, Root Length Density, Root Area Ratio, hazard mitigation*

27

Highlights

28

29

30

31

- Experiments show that rooting enhances soil stability and reduces debris-flow erosion.
- Root Length Density has a strong non-linear effect in reducing bed erosion.
- Seedlings offer potential for studying root effects on debris flows in experiments.

32

Graphical Abstract

What are the effects of roots on debris-flow erosion?

Scaled experiments provide insights on erosion processes.

Results indicate a reduction of erosion with an increase in Root Length Density.

1 Introduction

Debris flows are powerful and destructive mass movements that annually cost thousands of lives and billions of euros worldwide (Prakash et al., 2024). The number of casualties has been directly linked to debris-flow volume (Dowling & Santi, 2014), which may grow several orders of magnitude by bed and bank erosion during transport (e.g. Iverson et al., 2011; Jakob & Hungr, 2005). Therefore, understanding debris-flow erosion is important for effective hazard assessment and mitigation. Previous laboratory, modeling, and fieldwork studies have shown that debris-flow bed erosion depends on complex interactions between debris-flow forces and bed strength. Many flow properties have been correlated to bed erosion rates including volume (De Haas et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2005), depth (Schürch et al., 2011; McDougall & Hungr, 2005), velocity (Iverson, 2012; McDougall & Hungr, 2005), and basal, shear and impact forces (Roelofs et al., 2022; Li et al., 2020; Jakob & Hungr, 2005), where an increase in either of these factors generally enhances erosion. The resistance of the bed against erosion, or bed shear strength, has been found to depend strongly on the pore-pressure of the bed at the bed-flow interface. An increase in pore-pressure reduces intergranular friction and therefore weakens the bed shear strength (Zheng et al., 2023; Roelofs et al., 2023; Zheng et al., 2021; McCoy et al., 2012; Iverson, 2012). Vegetation roots are known to play a crucial role in improving bed, bank, and soil strength in both fluvial environments (Pollen, 2007; Pollen & Simon, 2005) and soil stability processes in mountainous environments (Draebing et al., 2023; Roering et al., 2003; Schmidt et al., 2001). By strengthening the soil matrix, they help resist erosion, reduce sediment transport, and mitigate the risk of slope failures. Roots resist tension forces and dissipate shear stresses through the soil using their tensile strength (Ghestem et al., 2014), increase shear strength by anchoring the soil (Poirier et al., 2018; Kaspar & Singer, 2011), and bind soil particles through adhesive secretions and chemical reactions with clay (Galloway et al., 2020; Poirier et al., 2018).

While previous studies documented debris flows interaction with plants in many mountain regions (Figure 1; Booth et al., 2020; Bollschweiler et al., 2008; Wilford et al., 2005; Bunn & Montgomery, 2004; Johnson et al., 2000), we have surprisingly little quantitative understanding of how roots affect debris-flow erosion. Field observations indicate that roots can reduce debris-flow erosion (Cui et al., 2024; Wilford et al., 2005). Months to years after wildfires, where the above-ground biomass is destroyed, erosion by debris flows peaks due to weakened soil strength as a result of root decay (Thomas et al., 2021; de Graff, 2018; Meyer et al., 2001). In industrial forests, debris flows often scour channels down to bedrock, whereas in old-growth forests with well-developed root structures, such scouring is rare (Schmidt et al., 2001; Bunn & Montgomery, 2004). On debris-flow fans, root webs are observed to offer resistance to debris-flow erosion (Figure 1b and d; Wilford et al., 2005). Combined with the well-documented role of plant roots in soil stability (e.g. Vannoppen et al., 2015; Ghestem et al., 2014; De Baets et al., 2007), these findings suggest that roots may play a vital role in reducing erosion caused by debris flows (Figure 2). Despite the significance, our understanding of the effect of roots on debris-flow erosion remains limited, mainly because of a lack of quantitative data. This lack results from the infrequent and destructive character of debris flows, making it hard to measure flow properties, root characteristics, bed strength, and interactions between debris flow and bed in the field (Iverson, 1997). As data on debris-flow forces and of root characteristics are limited, their combined influence on erosion dynamics remains even more poorly constrained.

To improve our insight into this poorly understood process, we aim to (1) unravel the impacts of plant roots on debris-flow erosion and (2) test the applicability of fast-growing seedlings to study debris flow—plant interactions in scaled laboratory experiments. Here, we present novel experiments in a small-scale debris-flow flume with an erodible sediment bed, in which we grow live seedlings to form beds with a wide range of root traits. Laboratory experiments enable systematic and quantitative exploration

Figure 1. Examples of interactions between debris flows and vegetation. (a) Post-wildfire debris flow in Jamestown, Colorado, November 2013 (White, 2013), (b) The root network in a forest stand strengthens the soil, enhancing its resistance to the development of new channels on a debris-flow fan; British Columbia, Canada (Wilford et al., 2005), (c) Debris flow running through a forested fan; Keze gully, China (Cui et al., 2024), (d) A debris flow gully formed after a forest fire, exposing roots protruding from the gully banks; Glenwood Canyon, Colorado, USA (with courtesy of Francis Rengers), (e) A scour hole formed by a debris flow after a forest fire; Glenwood Canyon, Colorado, USA (with courtesy of Francis Rengers) (f) Exposed roots after severe debris-flow erosion of a debris-flow fan; British Columbia, Canada (Wilford et al., 2005).

Figure 2. Sketch of (a) the primary forces driving debris flow erosion in the absence of vegetation, and (b) the additional mechanical effects of vegetation roots on debris-flow erosion reduction by increased soil cohesion and shear stress distribution through tensile strength.

86 of the effects of plant roots on debris-flow erosion under controlled conditions. In exper-
 87 iments, initial and boundary conditions can be precisely controlled, allowing for the isolation
 88 of individual variables. Debris flows have been successfully scaled in previous exper-
 89 iments, which, for example, increased our understanding of the effects of bed and debris-
 90 flow composition on erosion (Roelofs et al., 2023; Zheng et al., 2021), the seismic vibra-
 91 tions and normal-force fluctuations of debris flows (De Haas et al., 2021), and sediment
 92 trapping by vegetation (He et al., 2023). However, scant debris-flow experiments have
 93 been conducted with plant roots. Fast-growing seedlings have already been successfully
 94 used in other geomorphic experiments to study various earth surface processes (e.g. Lokhorst
 95 et al., 2019; De Baets et al., 2007), but their potential remains largely unexplored in debris-
 96 flow research. Such species offer several advantages, including the development of nat-
 97 ural root-soil contacts, a relatively short cultivation period, and the ability to alter root
 98 traits systematically. We conducted controlled laboratory experiments to quantify the
 99 effect of roots on debris-flow erosion. In this paper we do not test effects of above-ground
 100 biomass, which we removed, but focus on systematically varied root traits across exper-
 101 iments to identify key factors governing erosion reduction. The data generated could pro-
 102 vide insights into the effects of wildfires and deforestation on debris-flow erosion, par-
 103 ticularly when above-ground biomass is lost and remaining roots play a key role (Thomas
 104 et al., 2021; de Graff, 2018; Meyer et al., 2001). A better understanding of these processes
 105 would also contribute to more accurate debris-flow models and foster the development
 106 of strategies to reduce debris-flow erosion and mitigate its hazards.

107 **2 Methods**

108 To study the effect of roots on debris-flow erosion, we conducted 38 experiments
 109 in a flume with an erodible bed penetrated by natural roots. Each experiment's seed-
 110 ing densities and vegetation ages differed to vary root traits while keeping the bed and
 111 debris-flow composition constant. For each density, an experiment was conducted with
 112 5-day-old and 8-day-old vegetation to vary root length and diameter (see Table S1 for
 113 conditions of each experiment). The initial set of experiments was meant to determine
 114 the best experimental setup and to verify the applicability of the method. Therefore, each
 115 experimental setup was repeated once. The outcomes of these experiments are not in-
 116 cluded in the results. Once consistency and applicability were confirmed, subsequent ex-
 117 periments were conducted only once.

Figure 3. Schematic overview of the debris flow flume, with images showing the flume and the grown plants of 5 and 8 days old. All lengths are in centimeters.

2.1 Flume setup

The experiments were conducted in a debris-flow flume consisting of a 5.4 m long and 0.3 m wide channel inclined at 34° , a mixing tank with a forced-action mixer and custom-made release gate (set-up is similar to Roelofs et al. (2023) and De Haas et al. (2021); Figure 3). Five laser sensors captured flow hydrographs and velocities through time-distance measurements. Force fluctuations at the bed were measured using a Geospace GS-20DX geophone force plate (0.14 m wide, 0.06 m long), installed at 2.90 m and 2.98 m downstream of the release gate, recording seismic movement (vertical and horizontal) with a 10–1000 Hz response. The shear stress exerted by the debris flow on the bed was calculated as:

$$\tau = \rho g H \sin(S) \quad (1)$$

where τ is the shear stress (Pa), ρ is the density of the flow (kg/m^3), g is the gravitational acceleration (m/s^2), H is the flow depth (m), and S is the channel bed slope. In the lower 2.5 m of the channel, a vegetated erodible bed of 0.07 m thick was placed in a depression in the channel floor, of which the age and number of planted seeds were varied for each experiment. Bed elevation of the erodible bed was quantified before and after each experiment at sub-mm resolution with a Vialux z-Snapper three-dimensional scanner. From the measurements, the erosion volumes of the erodible bed were quantified by obtaining the difference in bed elevation before and after each experiment. The erosion rate was calculated by dividing the erosion volume by 1.5 seconds, as most erosion occurs within this time range under the influence of the boulder-rich debris flow front (Roelofs et al., 2023; De Haas et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2021). At 46 cm downstream of the start of the erodible bed, pore water pressures were measured at 3 and 4 cm below the surface (custom-made with Keller Pressure PR-23SY, with an accuracy of ± 0.25 %FS). Using a needle, water was inserted into the bed surrounding the pore-pressure measurement instruments to ensure saturated conditions.

144 For all experiments, debris-flow and bed compositions were kept constant (Table
 145 S2). Debris flows consisted of 75% sand, 5% clay (kaolin), 20% gravel, and a water frac-
 146 tion of 20% by weight (Figure 4a and b). The erodible bed was loosely packed and con-
 147 sisted of 96% sand and 4% clay (Figure 4c and d). The bed had a water fraction of 13%
 148 by weight (Table S2).

Figure 4. Grain size distributions used in the experiments. (a) Grain size distribution of the debris flow and erodible bed used for the experiments, (b) the cumulative grain size distribution of the debris flow and the erodible bed.

149 2.2 Describing flow characteristics

150 To compare the scaled debris flows with natural ones, the Bagnold, Savage, and
 151 friction numbers were calculated for each experiment. These numbers describe the re-
 152 lationship between the forces that resist motion in debris flows, comprising collisional,
 153 frictional, and viscous forces (Iverson, 1997). The Bagnold number compares collisional
 154 and viscous forces (Iverson, 1997):

$$155 N_b = \frac{v_s \rho_s \delta^2 \gamma}{v_f \mu} \quad (2)$$

156 where N_b is the Bagnold number (-), v_s is the volumetric solids fraction, ρ_s is the den-
 157 sity of the flow (kg/m³), δ is the mean grain size (m), v_f is the volumetric fraction of
 158 fines, γ is the flow shear rate (1/s):

$$159 \gamma = \frac{u}{H} \quad (3)$$

160 where u is the debris flow frontal velocity (m/s), and H is the maximum flow depth (m).
 161 The interstitial fluid viscosity μ is estimated as (De Haas et al., 2015; Iverson, 1997):

$$162 \frac{\mu}{\mu_w} = 1 + 2.5v_f + 10.05v_f^2 + 0.00273^{16.6v_f} \quad (4)$$

163 where μ_w is the dynamic viscosity of pure water (0.001002 Pa s). For $N_b > 200$, the col-
 164 lisional forces dominate the viscous forces (Iverson, 1997). The Savage number compares
 165 collisional and frictional forces:

$$166 N_s = \frac{\rho_s \delta^2 \gamma^2}{(\rho_s - \rho_f) g H \tan \phi'} \quad (5)$$

167 where ρ_f is the fluid density (kg/m³), and ϕ' is the angle of internal friction, estimated
 168 at 42° (De Haas et al., 2015). The collisional forces dominate the viscous forces when
 169 $N_s > 0.1$ (Iverson, 1997). Finally, frictional and viscous forces are compared with the
 170 friction number:

$$171 \quad N_f = \frac{v_s(\rho_s - \rho_f)gH \tan \phi'}{(1 - v_s)\gamma\mu} \quad (6)$$

172 For $N_f > 2000$, frictional forces dominate viscous forces (Iverson, 1997).

173 **2.3 Plant growth and quantification of root characteristics**

174 To simulate natural root-soil contact as present in the field, live seedlings of *Sorghum*
 175 *bicolor* were grown in the erodible bed. *S. bicolor* is a fast-growing seedling with a high
 176 germination rate and straight tap roots penetrating deep into the bed. Although the root
 177 architecture of *S. bicolor* is less complex than those of mature trees, it provides a practical
 178 and scalable proxy for studying root–soil interactions. Its roots exhibit similar mechanical
 179 effects in reinforcing soil and resisting erosion at small experimental scales (Lokhorst
 180 et al., 2019), enabling us to approximate the stabilizing effect of roots in a controlled setting.
 181 The tap root systems present in *S. bicolor* allow unambiguous data collection, processing,
 182 and interpretation. The seed density was based on Lokhorst et al. (2019), who
 183 showed that a density of 2 *seeds/cm*² is a typical density with measurable effects in small-scale
 184 geomorphic experiments of channel bank collapse and erosion by flow. Our seed
 185 density ranged from 0.4 to 6 *seeds/cm*². The average germination rate was 70%, gradually
 186 declining to approximately 50% throughout the experiments, likely due to the decrease
 187 in light caused by shorter daylight. This resulted in root densities ranging from
 188 0.3 to 4 *roots/cm*², assuming one root per seedling. Each sowing density was tested twice:
 189 once with plants grown for 5 days and once with plants grown for 8 days, which allowed
 190 for variation in root length and diameter. Before the start of each experiment, the above-ground
 191 biomass was cut off without disturbing the soil to isolate the effects of the roots
 192 on debris-flow erosion.

193 Before every experiment, we measured root length, root diameter, root density, root
 194 length density (*RLD*), root area ratio (*RAR*), and root tensile strength (*RTS*), considering
 195 that these root traits have been identified as most important for stabilizing soils
 196 and controlling erosion by overland flow (Vannoppen et al., 2015; Ghestem et al., 2014;
 197 Bischetti et al., 2009; De Baets et al., 2008; Ali & Osman, 2008; De Baets et al., 2007;
 198 Pollen, 2007). Root lengths and diameters were averaged over ten roots and measured
 199 using an electronic caliper with an accuracy of 0.01 mm. Root density was determined
 200 by counting the number of plants per unit of surface area. As we used tap roots in our
 201 experiments, the number of plants corresponds to the number of roots. *RLD* is used to
 202 quantify root distribution in soil, and was calculated as the root length per unit volume
 203 of soil (Figure 5a; Vannoppen et al., 2015; Ghestem et al., 2014; De Baets et al., 2007):

$$204 \quad RLD = \frac{\text{Root Length}}{\text{soil Volume}} \quad (7)$$

205 where the *RLD* is the Root Length Density (cm/cm³), the sum of the root lengths refers
 206 to the length of the total root system (cm) within the soil volume sampled (cm³), which
 207 translates to the volume of the erodible bed. For our experiments, the measured root
 208 lengths were scaled up based on the total number of counted roots. The *RAR* is defined
 209 as the fraction of a plane of soil occupied by roots per unit area (Figure 5b; Bierman &
 210 Montgomery, 2014; De Baets et al., 2008; Stokes et al., 2009):

211

$$RAR_d = \frac{A_r}{A} \quad (8)$$

212

213

214

where RAR_d is the Root Area Ratio (-), A_r is the root area per root (m^2), and A the area measured (m^2). The measured area is the width times the depth of the soil in the flume. The root area is calculated by:

215

$$A_r = \frac{\pi}{4} d^2 \quad (9)$$

216

217

where d is the root diameter (m). A different function to calculate RAR uses the RLD (De Baets et al., 2006):

218

$$RAR_{RLD} = RLD \times A_r \quad (10)$$

Figure 5. Illustration of the calculations of the concepts (a) RLD and (b) RAR , where W is the width, H is the height, and L is the length of the soil sample.

219

220

221

222

223

224

225

The apparent cohesion with roots (henceforth 'root cohesion') was calculated to assess the additional shear strength to the soil provided by roots. Root cohesion quantifies the effect of root traits on debris-flow erosion and allows for a comparison to the shear stress exerted by debris flows. Root cohesion was calculated using the Wu and Waldron model (Waldron, 1977; Alam et al., 2018; Wu, 1984), with both RAR_d and RAR_{RLD} as input. As our roots grow perpendicular to the soil and barely change position during shearing (Schmidt et al., 2001), root cohesion (C_r) is calculated as:

226

$$C_r = RTS \times RAR \quad (11)$$

227

228

229

The WWM model assumes that all roots break simultaneously, which we assume valid for fast-flowing debris flows. The RTS provides a measure of the roots' resistance to breaking as a result of shear and is calculated as:

230

$$RTS = \frac{F_{max}}{A_r} \quad (12)$$

231

232

where F_{max} is the maximum force that is exerted on a root before breaking (N), and A_r the root area (mm^2) (De Baets et al., 2008). For 26 roots, the diameter was measured

Figure 6. Characteristics of the debris flows measured during the experiments.

233 using an electronic caliper before conducting the breaking force test. The breaking force
 234 was determined by attaching roots of various diameters to a 100-gram PESOLA spring
 235 scale with a precision of $\pm 0.3\%$ (Hales et al., 2013). After attachment using UV resin,
 236 the roots were mechanically pulled at a controlled rate while recording the process on
 237 video. The exact moment of breakage was identified in the footage, and the correspond-
 238 ing force was recorded.

239 3 Results

240 3.1 Debris flow characteristics

241 The experimental debris flows were consistently characterized by a small amount
 242 of saltating and rolling gravel, followed by a debris flow with a steep, coarse flow front,
 243 ending in a tapering tail with finer sediments (see supporting video). The mean max-
 244 imum depth of the flow front was 5.2 cm, with a range from 4.5 to 0.56 cm (Figure 6a)
 245 and velocities ranged between 3.2 and 4.1 m/s (Figure 6b). The debris flows exerted a
 246 total shear stress of 3.8×10^6 to 1.1×10^7 kPa s (Figure 6c), and a vertical seismic en-
 247 ergy ranging from 8.0×10^{-7} to 2.7×10^{-6} (m/s)² (Figure 6d). The calculated Bag-
 248 nold numbers below 200 (90 - 130) indicate that viscous forces dominate over collisional
 249 forces (Figure 6e). Furthermore, as the Savage numbers remain below 0.1 and the fric-
 250 tional numbers exceed 2000, the debris flows investigated in these experiments are pri-
 251 marily governed by frictional forces (Figure 6f and g).

252 **Include link to video DFvideos.mp4 here please. Text for in article:**
 253 **Video documentation of debris flow flume experiments, including an overview**
 254 **of the flume setup and close-up footage of soil surface interaction during de-**
 255 **bris flow overrun.**

256 3.2 Root characteristics

257 Root traits changed during root growth. The 5-day-old vegetation was character-
 258 ized by an average root length of 27 millimeters, an average root diameter of 0.54 mil-

Figure 7. Correlation between root diameter and root tensile strength. The R^2 for the correlation is 0.69, and the p – value is below 0.001.

Figure 8. The development of root characteristics and bed change throughout the experiments, which are ordered with increasing sowing density. (a) The development in root density and root cohesion, calculated with RAR_{RLD} , and (b) the evolution of bed change.

259 limeters, and an absence of branching. In contrast, 8-day-old roots grew longer and thinned,
 260 on average 49 millimeters long and 0.47 millimeters in diameter. Some of the roots showed
 261 minor signs of branching, which were of negligible size for our experimental runs.

262 An increase in root diameter decreased the root tensile strength (Figure 7). The
 263 power law regression between root tensile strength and root diameter gives a statistically
 264 significant correlation between the parameters, in accordance with literature (e.g. De Baets
 265 et al., 2008; Genet et al., 2005).

266 Throughout the experiments, the sowing density, and therefore the root density,
 267 was increased (Table S1). With an increase in root density and root age, root cohesion
 268 increased simultaneously (Figure 8a), and the erosion decreased (Figure 8b). The anomaly
 269 observed in experiment 10 with 5-day-old vegetation can be attributed to the significantly
 270 shorter root length of 14 mm, which is 13 mm below the average for this age.

271 3.3 Spatial erosion patterns

272 Spatial erosion patterns were similar under different conditions, with scour at the
 273 upstream end of the erodible bed and alternating erosion and deposition throughout the
 274 rest of the bed (Figure 9). The scour at the upstream end of the bed decreased with an

Figure 9. Trends in erosion and deposition patterns in the erodible part of the flume, as a function of root density and age. The root density corresponds to (a) 0 roots/cm², (b) 0.28 roots/cm², (c) 0.83 roots/cm², (d) 1.3 roots/cm², (e) 2.3 roots/cm², (f) 3.6 roots/cm², (g) 0 roots/cm² (same as a), (h) 0.26 roots/cm², (i) 0.75 roots/cm², (j) 1.5 roots/cm², (k) 2.0 roots/cm², and (l) 3.3 roots/cm².

275 increase in root density and age (Figure 9). Additionally, the gullies that formed on beds
 276 without roots or with low root densities (Figure 9a, b, g and h) reduced in size on beds
 277 with higher root densities (Figure 9c), ultimately disconnecting to form scours (Figure
 278 9d-f and i-j) and disappearing on beds with 8-day-old, dense roots (Figure 9k and l). The
 279 scours originated on patches with little or no roots and progressively enlarged over the
 280 course of the debris flow. Depositional features formed on patches with a high root den-
 281 sity (Figure 9f and l).

3.4 Correlations between bed erosion and root traits

282
 283 Roots strongly affected debris-flow erosion volumes (Figure 10, Table S3). Beds with-
 284 out roots revealed increased erosion over beds with roots, where an increase in root den-
 285 sity led to a non-linear decrease in erosion (Figure 10a). 8-day-old vegetation was char-
 286 acterized by more developed roots, resulting in greater reduction of erosion compared
 287 to 5-day-old vegetation. An increase in RAR_d resulted in a non-linear decrease in ero-
 288 sion (Figure 10b). Notably, root density and RAR_d did not fully account for root age;
 289 the 5-day-old roots correlated with a greater bed change than the 8-day-old roots with
 290 the same root density or RAR_d . This indicates that some variation is left unexplained
 291 in these correlations, as root age should only affect the root traits, not the erosion. An
 292 increase in the root cohesion calculated from this RAR_d resulted in a non-linear decrease
 293 in erosion (Figure 10c). The trends differ between 5-day-old and 8-day-old roots, and
 294 mirror the correlation between RAR_d and erosion.

295 RLD exhibited a non-linear decrease in erosion with an increase in RLD (Figure
 296 10d). Importantly, RLD effectively accounts for the root ages by including the lesser pro-

Figure 10. Bed erosion volumes as a function of root traits: (a) root density, (b) RAR_d , (c) root cohesion calculated with RAR_d , (d) RLD , (e) RAR_{RLD} , and (f) root cohesion calculated with RAR_{RLD} . The dotted lines denote the regression lines for each correlation. The R^2 for each of these correlations ranges between 0.814–0.963, and the p -values are consistently <0.001 (Table S3). Note that a negative net change implies net erosion and a positive net change implies net deposition.

297 tection by the shorter 5-day-old vegetation, explaining most of the variation in the cor-
 298 relation between root traits and erosion. The RAR_{RLD} produced values ten times larger
 299 than the values calculated with the root diameters (Figure 10e). This adjusted RAR_{RLD}
 300 was associated with a non-linear decrease in erosion, where the difference between 5-day-
 301 old and 8-day-old roots is reduced compared to the RAR_d calculations (Figure 10b vs.
 302 e). The same holds for the non-linear correlation between the RAR_{RLD} and the bed change
 303 (Figure 10f). The root cohesion accounts for the roots' ages well, describing most of the
 304 variation between root cohesion and erosion.

305 4 Discussion

306 4.1 Effects of roots on debris-flow bed erosion

307 Our experiments showed that plant roots strongly reduce the magnitude of erosion
 308 by experimental debris flows (Figure 9 and 10). In our experiment, roots' impact on ero-
 309 sion changed with growth and age, altering the RAR and RLD , which can represent species-

specific traits in nature. Our observed decrease in erosion with an increase in root density, RAR , RLD , and root cohesion (Figure 10) can be explained by enlarging root-soil contact area, increasing enlacing and adhering properties (Vannoppen et al., 2015; Ghestem et al., 2014; De Baets et al., 2007; Zhou & Shangguan, 2005). Additionally, roots directly reduce shear stress on the bed underneath the debris flow by distributing tensile strength over a greater area (Ghestem et al., 2014; De Baets et al., 2008).

RLD exhibited the strongest correlation with erosion and encapsulated root characteristics regardless of root age (Figure 10d), suggesting that root length, combined with root density, plays a key role in reducing debris-flow erosion. As roots grow deeper, they increase root-soil contact and reduce the likelihood that erosion will occur below the root zone, where the roots would no longer be effective. Although RLD is often identified as the root trait that most strongly affects soil erosion (Vannoppen et al., 2015; Ghestem et al., 2014), most studies use RAR_d as a proxy for root cohesion (e.g. Bischetti et al., 2009; De Baets et al., 2008; Pollen, 2007), predominantly because it is easier to measure in the field than RLD (Vannoppen et al., 2015). Our results also revealed a decrease in erosion with an increase in RAR_d (Figure 10b). As root diameter, and thus RAR_d , increases, the soil-contact area increases simultaneously, enhancing soil shear strength (Ghestem et al., 2014; De Baets et al., 2008; Reubens et al., 2007; Gyssels & Poesen, 2003). However, the correlation between RAR_d and erosion did not account for root age (Figure 10b), which persisted in the calculations for root cohesion calculated with RAR_d (Figure 10c), in contrast to the correlation between RLD and erosion. Part of the unexplained variation can be attributed to the absence of root length in the calculation of RAR_d (equation 11). Furthermore, RAR_d expresses root area per unit soil cross-section, while RLD accounts for root distribution throughout the entire soil volume. Since root reinforcement affects the full soil matrix, RLD more comprehensively represents root-soil interactions and their impact on stability. Additionally, the RAR_d is less suitable for our experiments, as it assumes non-vertical root intersections with the plane (Stokes et al., 2009; Pollen, 2007). Since the roots used in our experiments are taproots, few roots grow this way.

Our experiments showed that high root length densities inhibited the formation of erosive bed forms. Scours typically develop in areas with low root length densities (Figure 9), leading to increased sediment transport and accelerated erosion (Roberts et al., 2022; Kirkby & Bracken, 2009; Johnson & Whipple, 2007). Similarly, areas with high root length densities exhibit smaller scours as a result of increased root cohesion (Figure 10b and f), thereby reducing erosion rates.

4.2 Incorporating RLD in debris-flow bed erosion rate calculations

To illustrate how root cohesion can be incorporated into debris-flow bed erosion equations, we integrated RLD into the erosion rate equation by Zheng et al. (2024). To achieve this, we created a dimensionless factor (E_{RLD}) that is a function of the RLD based on the correlation shown in Figure 10d:

$$E_{RLD} = 0.276 \ln(RLD) - 0.2707 \quad (13)$$

An E_{RLD} factor of 0 corresponds to no bed change, as the roots fully prevent erosion. An E_{RLD} factor of 1 corresponds to a bed without roots. Integrating this factor into the equation by Zheng et al. (2024) gives:

$$E_c = E_{RLD} \frac{\rho g h \sin S - (\rho g H \cos \theta - \mu_w) \tan \phi'}{\rho u} \quad (14)$$

Figure 11. Measured and fitted erosion rates for varying RLD values. The coefficient of determination is $R^2 = 0.93$ and the p -value of 2.87×10^{-9} , indicating a strong and statistically significant correlation.

355 where E_c is the erosion rate (cm/s), S is the flume angle (34°), and μ_w is pore-pressure
 356 (Pa).

357 Figure 11 shows the erosion rate as measured during the experiments and as calculated
 358 by equation 14. The calculated erosion rate reproduced the erosion rate measured
 359 during the experiments with promising accuracy, indicating that the equation effectively
 360 predicts a reduction in erosion as the RLD increases. The erosion rate was calculated
 361 assuming a bed pore-pressure of 350 Pa, which is in the range of bed pore-pressures
 362 measured in our experiments (200 - 500 Pa), and in accordance with values measured
 363 in similar experiments by Roelofs et al. (2023). Due to variations in pore-pressure with
 364 depth, distance from the erosion plane, and across debris-flow experiments, discrepancies
 365 may arise in the predictions generated by erosion models for debris flows. Although
 366 the direct applicability of the equation to field conditions needs further investigation, our
 367 findings distinctly showcase the potential of a correction factor based on RLD , which
 368 can be used to improve debris-flow erosion models.

369 4.3 Scaling effects

370 While scale experiments represent aspects of reality and may exhibit unwanted but
 371 limited scaling effects, the morphological and dynamic similarities between experimen-
 372 tal and natural debris flows enable controlled investigations of debris flow–bed interac-
 373 tions (Iverson & Denlinger, 2001; Paola et al., 2009; Kleinhans et al., 2014; De Haas &
 374 Woerkom, 2016). Both natural and experimental flows are thickest at the flow front, which
 375 has a high solid fraction and large grain sizes. The flows taper into a tail with lower ve-
 376 locities, increased wetness, and fine sediment (Mcardell, 2016; Iverson, 1997; De Haas
 377 et al., 2023). Furthermore, the dimensionless numbers characterizing flow dynamics and
 378 forces within a debris flow are dynamically similar to those of most natural debris flows,
 379 where frictional forces dominate debris-flow dynamics (Figure 6f and g, Roelofs et al.,
 380 2022; Zhou & Ng, 2010). Key factors influencing debris-flow erosion in the field,
 381 such as pore-pressure and bed shear strength, also play a role in our experiments. Fur-
 382 thermore, our scaled experiments successfully reproduce deposit characteristics of natu-
 383 ral debris flows (De Haas & Woerkom, 2016; Iverson, 2014; Wilford et al., 2004; Kim
 384 & Lowe, 2004; Pierson, 1986). The least erosion and occasionally even deposition is found
 385 on patches with high root densities, which is consistent with field observations, where
 386 well-developed root systems with higher RLD and RAR prevent deep scouring, and root
 387 webs are observed to resist erosion (Figure 1; Löbmann et al., 2020; Wirth, 2009; Wil-

388 ford et al., 2005; Bunn & Montgomery, 2004; Schmidt et al., 2001). Erosion was observed
389 between patches of roots, where root density was lower. This pattern agrees with field
390 observations, as root networks spread outward from trees, leading to lower root cohe-
391 sion and consequently more erosion (De Baets et al., 2007; Roering et al., 2003).

392 Table 4.3 presents the shear stresses and root traits measured during the exper-
393 iments, alongside values reported from the field. This comparison provides insight into
394 the relative magnitudes of forces governing debris-flow erosion. RTS in natural environ-
395 nments is often some order of magnitude greater than the shear stresses exerted by de-
396 bris flows, although the range is large. While RTS also exceeds shear stresses in our tests,
397 the difference in magnitude is less pronounced. Additionally, root cohesion in our exper-
398 iments is considerably lower than in field conditions. This discrepancy is expected, as
399 our setup features taproots distributed over a large area, whereas natural conditions are
400 often calculated per individual tree with a large root system. To compensate, we cre-
401 ated high root densities. However, root cohesion remains on the lower end, possibly due
402 to the experimental root simplicity. These deviations suggest that in our experiments,
403 the erosion may be higher than expected in natural settings. Nonetheless, this discrep-
404 ancy does not undermine the value of our experiments, as our primary goal is not to recre-
405 ate real-world conditions, but to isolate and study the interactions between debris flows
406 and plant roots. Despite the scaling differences, the combination of scaled debris flow
407 experiments and scaled roots enables a systematic study of debris flow-root interactions.
408 Our findings offer insight into how roots reinforce the soil and affect bed erosion, with
409 fundamental mechanisms and morphological features that are consistent between the lab-
410 oratory and the field.

411 **4.4 Small-scale, big impact: lab versus field observations**

412 Our research shows that there is high potential for using scaled live plants in debris-
413 flow experiments. This enables us to study the effects of plants on debris flows with a
414 degree of control that is not attainable in the field, and enables systematic exploration
415 of changes in boundary conditions and materials. Both modelling (e.g. Liu et al., 2021)
416 and field research (e.g. Tang et al., 2018; Michelini et al., 2017; Johnson et al., 2000)
417 have been done on plant–debris flow interactions, but these studies remain primarily
418 qualitative due to the lack of quantitative information regarding debris-flow forces and
419 plant traits. Our experimental study, for the first time, contributes quantitative knowl-
420 edge because we can control the root conditions.

421 Our pioneering tests offer many options for future expansion and improvement. Our
422 experiments were conducted using *S. bicolor* seedlings as a proxy for tree roots. Tree root
423 systems are typically characterized by extensive and hierarchical branching structures,
424 with roots varying in diameter, orientation, and length, and often interconnecting to form
425 complex networks (Ghestem et al., 2014; Bischetti et al., 2009). Moreover, natural en-
426 vironments host diverse tree species of varying ages, further increasing heterogeneity in
427 root architecture and mechanical behavior (Pohl et al., 2011; Stokes et al., 2009). Where
428 the simple root systems in our setup likely result in an underestimation of erosion re-
429 sistance, future experiments could employ plant species with more complex, multi-scale
430 root systems. Improving measurement of pore-pressure and water content could enhance
431 our understanding of how roots affect loading conditions and pore water transfer between
432 debris flow and bed, which is crucial for debris-flow erosion (Roelofs et al., 2023; Zheng
433 et al., 2023). Roots may reduce erosion by increasing permeability and enhancing drained
434 conditions (Liu et al., 2021; Kaspar & Singer, 2011; De Baets et al., 2011; Reubens et
435 al., 2007). Under these drained conditions, water and air can diffuse through the soil pores
436 without increasing pore-pressure, which helps maintain intergranular friction. However,
437 increased permeability could also facilitate the transfer of moisture and pore-pressure
438 from the debris flow to the bed, thereby increasing pore-pressure in the bed and poten-
439 tially enhancing erosion (Zheng et al., 2023). Furthermore, our experiments lacked above-

Table 1. Debris flow shear stresses measured during the experiments and during debris flow events in the field, along with root traits measured in the experiments and the field. The root cohesion from our experiments was calculated using RAR_{RLD} . The root traits given by Vergani et al. (2012) are measured in the Swiss Alps, the traits given by Bischetti et al. (2009) in the Italian Alps.

	Shear stress	RTS	Root cohesion
	KPa	N/mm ²	KPa
Our experiments	0.47–0.59	0.85–1.8	1.9×10^{-4} – 4.3×10^{-3}
..... Illgraben ^{a, b}	0.37–5.1		
Roßbichelbach (modeled) ^c	4–15		
Montecito, USA ^d	1.6		
..... Acer pseudoplatanus ^e		3.68–31.48	
Castanea sativa ^{e,f}		0.81–45	8.1–19.6
Fagus sylvatica ^{e,f}		3.38–75.22	14.4–86
Fraxinus excelsior ^e		3.89–24.91	
Larix decidua ^{e,f}		1.03–110	17.4–38.3
Ostrya carpinifolia ^{e,f}		1.8–30.17	5.4–30
Picea abies ^{e,f}		2.84–95	13.8–35.4

^a de Haas et al. (2022)

^b Berger et al. (2011)

^c Dietrich & Krautblatter (2019)

^d Kostynick et al. (2025)

^e Vergani et al. (2012)

^f Bischetti et al. (2009)

440 ground biomass, which could reduce debris flow energy and size through obstructions
 441 (Liu et al., 2021; Michelini et al., 2017). However, above-ground biomass simultaneously
 442 increases the chances of root pullout, decreasing the soil strength and increasing erosion
 443 (Chen et al., 2024; Stokes et al., 2009). Further research could improve our under-
 444 standing of the combined effect of above and below-ground biomass on debris-flow in-
 445 duced erosion.

446 Our findings suggest that preventing cuttings or even planting trees on debris-flow
 447 fans and catchments can serve as effective strategies for mitigating debris-flow hazards,
 448 as an increase in RLD and RAR decreases erosion and therefore diminishes the volume
 449 and impact of a debris flow. Further experiments, modeling that represents the rooting
 450 density and structure, and additional field data will be essential for deepening our un-
 451 derstanding and the predictability of these processes.

452 5 Conclusions

453 We experimentally investigated the effects of plant roots on debris-flow erosion to
 454 gain a better understanding of the interaction between debris flows and trees. By com-
 455 bining measurements of debris-flow characteristics, erosion, and root traits, we were able
 456 to quantify the reduction of debris-flow induced erosion by roots compared to rootless
 457 beds. While our setup simplifies natural root structures and conditions and isolates ef-

458 facts of below-ground biomass from effects of above-ground biomass, it enables a controlled study of fundamental erosion mechanisms.
459

460 Our experiments showed a clear non-linear relationship between *RLD* and debris-flow bed erosion, with minimal difference between 5-day-old and 8-day-old roots. *RAR*
461 and root cohesion followed the same non-linear trend when calculated from *RLD*, indicating that the combined effect of root length and root density is an important factor
462 for reducing debris-flow bed erosion. These results imply a potential application: vegetating debris-flow-prone slopes could reduce erosion and flow volume growth, thereby
463 lessening their hazardous impact. The results also offer insight needed for hazard assessment: after wildfires, root decay may weaken root cohesion, increasing susceptibility to
464 erosion and enhancing debris-flow volume and hazards.
465
466
467
468

469 Our results demonstrate that small-scale debris-flow experiments with live seedlings can provide valuable insights into the effects of plants on debris-flow erosion that are challenging to investigate in the field. Further experimental exploration can provide a scientific basis for the mitigation of debris-flow hazards using nature-based solutions and give insights into the effects of changing vegetation due to wildfires and deforestation on debris-flow hazards. Our findings point to a new pathway towards incorporating root characteristics into erosion models, and show the importance of vegetation in debris-flow-prone areas.
470
471
472
473
474
475
476

477 **Open Research**

478 Experimental data, including pre- and post-flow DEMs, flow measurements, and the root trait measurements are available via Yoda (online repository of Utrecht University) under this link: <https://public.yoda.uu.nl/geo/UU01/NYY5H3.html>. DOI: 10.24416/UU01-NYY5H3.
479
480
481

482 **Acknowledgements**

483 This work was supported by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) (grant VI.Vidi.233.008 to TdH). The authors gratefully acknowledge the help of Arjan van Eijk, Bas van Dam, Marcel van Maarseveen, and Henk Markies in designing and constructing the flume and measurement set-ups, as well as their assistance during the experiments. We would also like to thank Caitlin Amels en Jelle Posthuma for helping out with the pre-experiments.
484
485
486
487

488 **Sample CRediT author statement**

489 **Anna J. van den Broek:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Formal analysis, Visualization. **Dagmar T. Mennes:** Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Maarten G. Kleinhans:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Lonneke Roelofs:** Writing - Review & Editing. **Jana Eichel:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Daniel Draebing:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Tjalling de Haas:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.
490
491
492
493
494
495

496 **References**

- 497 Alam, S., Banjara, A., Wang, J., Patterson, W., & Baral, S. (2018). Novel approach in sampling and tensile strength evaluation of roots to enhance soil
498 for preventing erosion. *Open Journal of Soil Science*, 8, 330-349. doi:
499 10.4236/ojss.2018.812024
500
501 Ali, F. H., & Osman, N. (2008). Shear strength of a soil containing vegetation roots. *Soils and Foundations*, 48(4), 587-596. doi: 10.3208/sandf.48.587
502

- 503 Bierman, P., & Montgomery, D. (2014). *Key concepts in geomorphology*. W.H. Free-
504 man.
- 505 Bischetti, G. B., Chiaradia, E. A., Epis, T., & Morlotti, E. (2009). Root cohesion
506 of forest species in the Italian Alps. *Plant and Soil*, 324, 71–89. doi: 10.1007/
507 s11104-009-9941-0
- 508 Bollschweiler, M., Stoffel, M., & Schneuwly, D. M. (2008, 1). Dynamics in debris-
509 flow activity on a forested cone - A case study using different dendroecological
510 approaches. *Catena*, 72(1), 67–78. doi: 10.1016/j.catena.2007.04.004
- 511 Booth, A. M., Sifford, C., Vascik, B., Siebert, C., & Buma, B. (2020). Large wood
512 inhibits debris flow runout in forested southeast Alaska. *Earth Surface Pro-
513 cesses and Landforms*, 45(7), 1555–1568. doi: 10.1002/esp.4830
- 514 Bunn, J. T., & Montgomery, D. R. (2004). Patterns of Wood and Sediment Stor-
515 age Along Debris-Flow Impacted Headwater Channels in Old-Growth and
516 Industrial Forests of the Western Olympic Mountains, Washington. In *Ri-
517 parian vegetation and fluvial geomorphology* (Vol. 8, pp. 99–112). American
518 Geophysical Union. doi: 10.1029/008WSA08
- 519 Chen, J., He, Y., & Wei, F. (2005). Debris flow erosion and deposition in Jiangjia
520 gully, Yunnan, China. *Environmental Geology*, 48, 771–777. doi: 10.1007/
521 s00254-005-0017-z
- 522 Chen, X., Jin, K., Wang, C., Liu, H., Zhao, W., & Chen, J. (2024). Tree fail-
523 ure modes influenced by the characteristics of tree and its root distribution
524 caused by debris flows. *Journal of Mountain Science*, 21(12), 3986–4000. doi:
525 10.1007/s11629-024-8887-2
- 526 Cui, W. R., Chen, J. G., Chen, X. Q., Song, D. R., Zhao, W. Y., & Jin, K.
527 (2024). Effect of topographic slope on the interaction between debris
528 flows and riparian forests. *Landslides*, 21, 889–900. Retrieved from
529 <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10346-023-02183-8> doi:
530 10.1007/s10346-023-02183-8/TABLES/6
- 531 De Baets, S., Poesen, J., Gysels, G., & Knapen, A. (2006). Effects of grass roots on
532 the erodibility of topsoils during concentrated flow. *Geomorphology*, 76, 54–67.
533 doi: 10.1016/j.geomorph.2005.10.002
- 534 De Baets, S., Poesen, J., Knapen, A., & Galindo, P. (2007). Impact of root architec-
535 ture on the erosion-reducing potential of roots during concentrated flow. *Earth
536 Surface Processes and Landforms: The Journal of the British Geomorphologi-
537 cal Research Group*, 32(9), 1323–1345. doi: 10.1002/esp
- 538 De Baets, S., Poesen, J., Meersmans, J., & Serlet, L. (2011). Cover crops and their
539 erosion-reducing effects during concentrated flow erosion. *Catena*, 85(3), 237–
540 244. doi: 10.1016/j.catena.2011.01.009
- 541 De Baets, S., Poesen, J., Reubens, B., Wemans, K., De Baerdemaeker, J., & Muys,
542 B. (2008). Root tensile strength and root distribution of typical Mediterranean
543 plant species and their contribution to soil shear strength. *Plant and Soil*, 305,
544 207–226. doi: 10.1007/s11104-008-9553-0
- 545 de Graff, J. V. (2018). A rationale for effective post-fire debris flow mitiga-
546 tion within forested terrain. *Geoenvironmental Disasters*, 5(7). doi:
547 10.1186/s40677-018-0099-z
- 548 De Haas, T., Åberg, A. S., Walter, F., & Zhang, Z. (2021). Deciphering seismic and
549 normal-force fluctuation signatures of debris flows: An experimental assess-
550 ment of effects of flow composition and dynamics. *Earth Surface Processes and
551 Landforms*, 46(11), 2195–2210. doi: 10.1002/esp.5168
- 552 De Haas, T., Braat, L., Leuven, J. R., Lokhorst, I. R., & Kleinhans, M. G. (2015).
553 Effects of debris flow composition on runout, depositional mechanisms, and de-
554 posit morphology in laboratory experiments. *Journal of Geophysical Research:
555 Earth Surface*, 120, 1949–1972. doi: 10.1002/2015JF003525
- 556 De Haas, T., McARDell, B., Nijland, W., Åberg, A., Hirschberg, J., De Jong, S.,
557 & Huguenin, P. (2023, 8). Factors controlling bed and bank erosion in the

- Illgraben (CH). In *E3s web of conferences* (Vol. 415). EDP Sciences. doi: 10.1051/e3sconf/202341501004
- De Haas, T., McArdeall, B., Nijland, W., Åberg, A., Hirschberg, J., & Huguenin, P. (2022). Flow and bed conditions jointly control debris-flow erosion and bulking. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 49(10), e2021GL097611. doi: 10.1029/2021GL097611
- De Haas, T., & Woerkom, T. v. (2016). Bed scour by debris flows: experimental investigation of effects of debris-flow composition. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 41(13), 1951–1966. doi: 10.1002/esp.3963
- Dowling, C. A., & Santi, P. M. (2014). Debris flows and their toll on human life: a global analysis of debris-flow fatalities from 1950 to 2011. *Natural hazards*, 71, 203–227. doi: 10.1007/s11069-013-0907-4
- Draebing, D., Gebhard, T., & Pheiffer, M. (2023). Geology and vegetation control landsliding on forest-managed slopes in scarplands. *Earth Surface Dynamics*, 11, 71–88. doi: 10.5194/esurf-11-71-2023
- Galloway, A. F., Knox, P., & Krause, K. (2020). Sticky mucilages and exudates of plants: putative microenvironmental design elements with biotechnological value. *New Phytologist*, 225(4), 1461–1469. doi: 10.1111/nph.16144
- Genet, M., Stokes, A., Salin, F., Mickovski, S. B., Fourcaud, T., Dumail, J.-F., & Van Beek, R. (2005). The influence of cellulose content on tensile strength in tree roots. *Plant and soil*, 278, 1–9. doi: 10.1007/s11104-005-8768-6
- Ghestem, M., Veylon, G., Bernard, A., Vanel, Q., & Stokes, A. (2014). Influence of plant root system morphology and architectural traits on soil shear resistance. *Plant and soil*, 377, 43–61. doi: 10.1007/s11104-012-1572-1
- Gyssels, G., & Poesen, J. (2003). The importance of plant root characteristics in controlling concentrated flow erosion rates. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms: The Journal of the British Geomorphological Research Group*, 28(4), 371–384. doi: 10.1002/esp.447
- Hales, T. C., Cole-Hawthorne, C., Lovell, L., & Evans, S. L. (2013). Assessing the accuracy of simple field based root strength measurements. *Plant and Soil*, 372, 553–565. doi: 10.1007/s11104-013-1765-2
- He, S., Chen, W., Wang, D., Chen, X., Qi, Y., Zhao, P., ... Jamali, A. A. (2023). Experimental investigation of the effects of shrub filter strips on debris flow trapping and interception. *International Journal of Sediment Research*, 38, 265–278. doi: 10.1016/j.ijsrc.2022.09.005
- Iverson, R. M. (1997). The physics of debris flows. *Reviews of geophysics*, 35(3), 245–296. doi: 10.1029/97RG00426
- Iverson, R. M. (2012). Elementary theory of bed-sediment entrainment by debris flows and avalanches. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, 117(F3). doi: 10.1029/2011JF002189
- Iverson, R. M. (2014). Debris flows: behaviour and hazard assessment. *Geology today*, 30(1), 15–20. doi: 10.1111/gto.12037
- Iverson, R. M., & Denlinger, R. P. (2001). Flow of variably fluidized granular masses across three-dimensional terrain: 1. coulomb mixture theory. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 106(B1), 537–552. doi: 10.1029/2000JB900329
- Iverson, R. M., Reid, M. E., Logan, M., LaHusen, R. G., Godt, J. W., & Griswold, J. P. (2011). Positive feedback and momentum growth during debris-flow entrainment of wet bed sediment. *Nature Geoscience*, 4(2), 116–121. doi: 10.1038/ngeo1040
- Jakob, M., & Hungr, O. (2005). *Debris-flow hazard analysis and related phenomena*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. doi: 10.1007/3-540-27129-5
- Johnson, A., Swanston, D., & McGee, K. (2000). Landslide initiation, runout, and deposition within clearcuts and old-growth forests of alaska. *JAWRA Journal of the American Water Resources Association*, 36(1), 17–30. doi:

- 10.1111/j.1752-1688.2000.tb04245.x
- 613 Johnson, J. P., & Whipple, K. X. (2007). Feedbacks between erosion and sedi-
614 ment transport in experimental bedrock channels. *Earth Surface Processes*
615 *and Landforms: The Journal of the British Geomorphological Research Group*,
616 32(7), 1048–1062. doi: 10.1002/esp.1471
- 617 Kaspar, T., & Singer, J. (2011). The use of cover crops to manage soil.
618 *Soil management: Building a stable base for agriculture*, 321–337. doi:
619 10.2136/2011.soilmanagement.c21
- 620 Kim, B. C., & Lowe, D. R. (2004). Depositional processes of the gravelly debris
621 flow deposits, south dolomite alluvial fan, Owens Valley, California. *Geosciences*
622 *Journal*, 8, 153–170. doi: 10.1007/BF02910191
- 623 Kirkby, M., & Bracken, L. (2009). Gully processes and gully dynamics. *Earth Sur-*
624 *face Processes and Landforms: The Journal of the British Geomorphological*
625 *Research Group*, 34(14), 1841–1851. doi: 10.1002/esp.1866
- 626 Kleinhans, M. G., van Dijk, W. M., van de Lageweg, W. I., Hoyal, D. C., Markies,
627 H., van Maarseveen, M., ... others (2014). Quantifiable effectiveness of
628 experimental scaling of river-and delta morphodynamics and stratigraphy.
629 *Earth-Science Reviews*, 133, 43–61. doi: 10.1016/j.earscirev.2014.03.001
- 630 Li, P., Wang, J., Hu, K., & Wang, F. (2020). Experimental study of debris-flow en-
631 trainment over stepped-gradient beds incorporating bed sediment porosity. *En-*
632 *gineering Geology*, 274, 105708. doi: 10.1016/j.enggeo.2020.105708
- 633 Liu, W., Yang, Z., & He, S. (2021). Modeling the landslide-generated debris flow
634 from formation to propagation and run-out by considering the effect of vegeta-
635 tion. *Landslides*, 18, 43–58. doi: 10.1007/s10346-020-01478-4
- 636 Löbmann, M. T., Geitner, C., Wellstein, C., & Zerbe, S. (2020). The influence of
637 herbaceous vegetation on slope stability – A review. *Earth-Science Reviews*,
638 209, 103328. doi: 10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103328
- 639 Lokhorst, I. R., de Lange, S. I., van Buiten, G., Selaković, S., & Kleinhans, M. G.
640 (2019). Species selection and assessment of eco-engineering effects of seedlings
641 for biogeomorphological landscape experiments. *Earth Surface Processes and*
642 *Landforms*, 44(14), 2922–2935. doi: 10.1002/esp.4702
- 643 McCardell, B. W. (2016). Field Measurements of Forces in Debris Flows at the Ill-
644 graben: Implications for Channel-Bed Erosion. *International Journal of Ero-*
645 *sion Control Engineering*, 9(4). doi: <https://doi.org/10.13101/ijece.9.194>
- 646 McCoy, S., Kean, J. W., Coe, J. A., Tucker, G., Staley, D. M., & Wasklewicz, T.
647 (2012). Sediment entrainment by debris flows: In situ measurements from
648 the headwaters of a steep catchment. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth*
649 *Surface*, 117(F3).
- 650 McDougall, S., & Hungr, O. (2005). Dynamic modelling of entrainment in rapid
651 landslides. *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 42(5), 1437–1448. doi: 10.1139/t05-
652 -064
- 653 Meyer, G. A., Pierce, J. L., Wood, S. H., & Jull, A. J. (2001). Fire, storms, and
654 erosional events in the Idaho batholith. *Hydrological Processes*, 15, 3025–3038.
655 doi: 10.1002/hyp.389
- 656 Michelini, T., Bettella, F., & D’Agostino, V. (2017). Field investigations of the inter-
657 action between debris flows and forest vegetation in two alpine fans. *Geomor-*
658 *phology*, 279, 150–164. doi: 10.1016/j.geomorph.2016.09.029
- 659 Paola, C., Straub, K., Mohrig, D., & Reinhardt, L. (2009). The “unreasonable effec-
660 tiveness” of stratigraphic and geomorphic experiments. *Earth-Science Reviews*,
661 97(1-4), 1–43. doi: 10.1016/j.earscirev.2009.05.003
- 662 Pierson, T. C. (1986). Flow behavior of channelized debris flows, Mount St. Helens,
663 Washington. In *Hillslope processes* (pp. 269–296). Routledge. doi: 10.4324/
664 9781003028840-13
- 665 Pohl, M., Stroude, R., Buttler, A., & Rixen, C. (2011). Functional traits and root
666 morphology of alpine plants. *Annals of Botany*, 108, 537–545. doi: 10.18280/
667

668
669
670
671
672
673
674
675
676
677
678
679
680
681
682
683
684
685
686
687
688
692
693
694
695
696
697
698
699
700
701
702
703
704
705
706
707
708
709
710
711
712
713
714
715
716
717
718
719
720
721
722

ijht.350120

- Poirier, V., Roumet, C., & Munson, A. D. (2018). The root of the matter: Linking root traits and soil organic matter stabilization processes. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 120, 246–259. doi: 10.1016/j.soilbio.2018.02.016
- Pollen, N. (2007). Temporal and spatial variability in root reinforcement of stream-banks: Accounting for soil shear strength and moisture. *Catena*, 69(3), 197–205. doi: 10.1016/j.catena.2006.05.004
- Pollen, N., & Simon, A. (2005). Estimating the mechanical effects of riparian vegetation on stream bank stability using a fiber bundle model. *Water Resources Research*, 41, W07025. doi: 10.1029/2004WR003801
- Prakash, N., Santi, P., Strouth, A., Sepulveda, S. A., & Dowling, C. (2024). Fatalities from debris flows: Worldwide distribution and trends. In *Advances in debris-flow science and practice* (pp. 75–91). Springer. doi: 10.18356/79b92774-en
- Reubens, B., Poesen, J., Danjon, F., Geudens, G., & Muys, B. (2007). The role of fine and coarse roots in shallow slope stability and soil erosion control with a focus on root system architecture: a review. *Trees*, 21(4), 385–402. doi: 10.1007/s00468-007-0132-4
- Roberts, M. E., Burrows, R. M., Thwaites, R. N., & Hamilton, D. P. (2022). Modelling classical gullies—a review. *Geomorphology*, 407, 108216. doi: 10.1016/j.geomorph.2022.108216
- Roelofs, L., Colucci, P., & De Haas, T. (2022). How debris-flow composition affects bed erosion quantity and mechanisms: An experimental assessment. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 47(8), 2151–2169. Retrieved from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/esp.5369> doi: 10.1002/esp.5369
- Roelofs, L., Nota, E. W., Flipsen, T. C., Colucci, P., & De Haas, T. (2023). How bed composition affects erosion by debris flows—an experimental assessment. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 50(14), e2023GL103294. doi: 10.1029/2023GL103294
- Roering, J. J., Schmidt, K. M., Stock, J. D., Dietrich, W. E., & Montgomery, D. R. (2003). Shallow landsliding, root reinforcement, and the spatial distribution of trees in the Oregon Coast Range. *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 40(2), 237–253. doi: 10.1139/t02-113
- Schmidt, K. M., Roering, J. J., Stock, J. D., Dietrich, W. E., Montgomery, D. R., & Schaub, T. (2001, 10). The variability of root cohesion as an influence on shallow landslide susceptibility in the Oregon Coast Range. *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 38(5), 995–1024. doi: 10.1139/cgj-38-5-995
- Schürch, P., Densmore, A. L., Rosser, N. J., & McArdell, B. W. (2011). Dynamic controls on erosion and deposition on debris-flow fans. *Geology*, 39(9), 827–830. doi: 10.1130/G32103.1
- Stokes, A., Atger, C., Bengough, A., Fourcaud, T., & Sidle, R. (2009). Desirable plant root traits for protecting natural and engineered slopes against landslides. *Plant Soil*, 324, 1–30. doi: 10.1007/s11104-009-0159-y
- Tang, Y.-J., Xu, Z.-M., Yang, T.-Q., Zhou, Z.-H., Wang, K., Ren, Z., ... Tian, L. (2018). Impacts of small woody debris on slurring, persistence, and propagation in a low-gradient channel of the dongyuege debris flow in nu river, southwest china. *Landslides*, 15, 2279–2293. doi: 10.1007/s10346-018-1036-7
- Thomas, M. A., Rengers, F. K., Kean, J. W., McGuire, L. A., Staley, D. M., Barnhart, K. R., & Ebel, B. A. (2021). Postwildfire soil-hydraulic recovery and the persistence of debris flow hazards. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, 126(6), e2021JF006091. doi: 10.1029/2021JF006091

- 723 Vannoppen, W., Vanmaercke, M., De Baets, S., & Poesen, J. (2015). A review of
724 the mechanical effects of plant roots on concentrated flow erosion rates. *Earth-*
725 *Science Reviews*, 150, 666–678. doi: 10.1016/j.earscirev.2015.08.011
- 726 Vergani, C., Chiaradia, E. A., & Bischetti, G. B. (2012). Variability in the tensile
727 resistance of roots in Alpine forest tree species. *Ecological Engineering*, 46, 43–
728 56. doi: 10.1016/j.ecoleng.2012.04.036
- 729 Waldron, L. (1977). The shear resistance of root-permeated homogeneous and strat-
730 ified soil. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 41(5), 843–849. doi: 10
731 .2136/sssaj1977.03615995004100050005x
- 732 White, J. (2013, 11). Debris and Mud Flows: Post-wildfire de-
733bris flow from the “1,000-year rain event” in September near
734 Jamestown, Colorado, November 2013. *Colorado Geological Survey*;
735 <https://coloradogeologicalsurvey.org/hazards/debris-flows/> .
- 736 Wilford, D. J., Sakals, M., Innes, J., Sidle, R. C., & Bergerud, W. (2004). Recogni-
737 tion of debris flow, debris flood and flood hazard through watershed morpho-
738 metrics. *Landslides*, 1(1), 61–66. doi: 10.1007/s10346-003-0002-0
- 739 Wilford, D. J., Sakals, M. E., Innes, J. L., & Sidle, R. C. (2005). Fans with
740 forests: contemporary hydrogeomorphic processes on fans with forests
741 in west central British Columbia, Canada. In *Alluvial Fans: Geomor-*
742 *phology, Sedimentology, Dynamics*. Geological Society of London. doi:
743 10.1144/GSL.SP.2005.251.01.03
- 744 Wirth, C. (2009). Old-growth forests: Function, fate and value – a synthesis. In
745 C. Wirth, G. Gleixner, & M. Heimann (Eds.), *Old-growth forests: Function,*
746 *fate and value* (pp. 465–491). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
747 Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-92706-8_21 doi:
748 10.1007/978-3-540-92706-8_21
- 749 Wu, T. H. (1984). Effect of vegetation on slope stability. *Transportation Research*
750 *Record*, 965, 37–46.
- 751 Zheng, H., Hu, X., Shi, Z., Shen, D., & De Haas, T. (2024). Deciphering controls
752 of pore-pressure evolution on sediment bed erosion by debris flows. *Geophysical*
753 *Research Letters*, 51(5), e2024GL108583. doi: 10.1029/2024GL108583
- 754 Zheng, H., Shi, Z., Hanley, K. J., Zhou, Y., & Hu, X. (2023). Pore pressure evolu-
755 tion in bed sediment overridden by debris flow: A general formulation. *Earth*
756 *Surface Processes and Landforms*, 48(6), 1188–1201. doi: 10.1002/esp.5542
- 757 Zheng, H., Shi, Z., Yu, S., Fan, X., Hanley, K., & Feng, S. (2021). Erosion mech-
758 anisms of debris flow on the sediment bed. *Water Resources Research*, 57(12),
759 e2021WR030707. doi: 10.1029/2021WR030707
- 760 Zhou, G. G., & Ng, C. W. (2010). Dimensional analysis of natural debris flows.
761 *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 47(7), 719–729. doi: 10.1139/T09-134
- 762 Zhou, Z.-C., & Shangguan, Z.-P. (2005). Soil anti-scourability enhanced by plant
763 roots. *Journal of Integrative Plant Biology*, 47(6), 676–682. doi: 10.1111/j
764 .1744-7909.2005.00067.x

Supplementary material**Table S1.** Overview of the changed boundary conditions of each experiment.

Exp nmr	Age roots	Sowed den- sity	Root den- sity	RLD	RAR_d	C_r	RAR_{RLD}	C_r with RLD
	<i>days</i>	<i>seeds/cm³</i>	<i>roots/cm³</i>	<i>cm/cm³</i>	<i>– ×10⁻⁵</i>	<i>MPa ×10⁻²</i>	<i>– ×10⁻⁴</i>	<i>MPa ×10⁻³</i>
1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3a	5	0.4	0.28	0.10	0.647	0.79	1.55	0.189
3b	8	0.4	0.26	0.16	0.721	0.771	3.16	0.338
4a	5	0.5	0.41	0.13	1.31	1.12	3.03	0.259
4b	8	0.5	0.33	0.21	0.981	0.981	4.30	0.430
5a	5	0.76	0.60	0.20	1.92	1.82	4.47	0.422
5b	8	0.76	0.46	0.28	1.26	1.33	5.40	0.569
6a	5	1	0.83	0.48	2.08	2.14	8.48	0.874
6b	8	1	0.75	0.59	1.61	1.85	8.91	1.02
7a	5	1.4	1.1	0.36	3.91	3.37	9.28	0.799
7b	8	1.4	0.87	0.65	1.15	2.10	5.99	1.09
8a	5	2	1.3	0.53	4.03	3.93	11.4	1.11
8b	8	2	1.5	1.21	3.57	4.11	20.6	2.37
9a	5	3	2.3	0.88	6.99	6.80	18.9	1.83
9b	8	3	2.0	1.46	3.61	5.25	18.4	2.67
10a	5	4	2.1	0.42	7.46	6.64	10.3	0.913
10b	8	4	2.0	1.27	4.98	5.65	22.4	2.55
11a	5	6	3.6	0.98	12.9	11.3	24.9	2.19
11b	8	6	3.3	2.14	8.44	9.47	38.4	4.31

Table S2. Key characteristics of the experimental settings of the flume experiments, including the varied root densities and the debris flow composition and characteristics.

Debris flow components	Unit	Values
Clay (kaolin)	dry weight fraction	0.05
	kg	2.4
Sand	dry weight fraction	0.75
	kg	36
Gravel	dry weight fraction	0.2
	kg	9.6
Water	dry weight fraction	0.2
	kg	12
Flume settings	Unit	Value
Flume angle	degrees	34°
Bed components	Unit	Values
Clay (kaolin)	dry weight fraction	0.04
Sand	dry weight fraction	0.96
Water	dry weight fraction	0.13
Number of seeds	Unit	Tested range
Seed density	<i>seeds/cm²</i>	0.4 – 6

Table S3. Results of the regression analysis for the correlation between the net bed change and the variables calculated from the measured traits. The logarithmic regression is described as $bedchange = a \log(variable) + b$

plant age	Constant a	Constant b	R²	p-value
<i>Root density</i>				
5-day	2079	-3717	0.878	1.96×10^{-4}
8-day	2376	-1838	0.948	2.29×10^{-6}
<i>Root length density</i>				
5-day	2254	-1300	0.936	1.97×10^{-5}
8-day	2278	-998.3	0.963	2.89×10^{-6}
<i>Root area ratio (RAR_d)</i>				
5-day	1774	14720	0.817	8.29×10^{-4}
8-day	2299	22710	0.814	8.62×10^{-4}
<i>Root area ratio (RAR_{RLD})</i>				
5-day	2022	10860	0.917	4.97×10^{-5}
8-day	2298	13790	0.868	2.59×10^{-4}
<i>Root cohesion calculated with (RAR_d)</i>				
5-day	1938	-16510	0.8531	3.75×10^{-4}
8-day	2368	23030	0.916	5.18×10^{-5}
<i>Root cohesion calculated with (RAR_{RLD})</i>				
5-day	2169	12020	0.9339	1.59×10^{-5}
8-day	2305	13420	0.9452	1.15×10^{-5}